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Investigating Citizen Science

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Maintenance and Legacy for Community Platform

D5.3

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Executive summary	This deliverable submitted at the end of the 34th month of the project shows the results of work carried out over 24 months dedicated to the maintenance and legacy of the CS Track Community Platform published in cstrack.eu To guarantee the sustainability of the Community Platform, this deliverable provides the necessary technical and editorial documentation showing how to use it, including back-up practices, data policy and comprehensive documentation of

the legacy of the platform and content published in the eMagazine.

To contextualize the legacy information and facilitate the operation of the Community Platform in the future, the document offers a historical review of the actions taken to include successive improvements in the Community Platform to contextualize the updates done, and the result obtained.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable shows the results of a significant amount of work developed over a 24-month period addressed to the evolution and legacy of the CS Track Community Platform published on cstrack.eu. Likewise, it provides the necessary information for the maintenance and sustainability of the website after the end of the project.

Previously, the Deliverable D5.1 explained the technical requirements and implementation plan for this Community Platform based on the technical and user needs of the consortium partners. A breakdown of the functional requirements for the dashboard, eMagazine and newsletter is detailed. As indicated in deliverable D5.1, some aspects of the eMagazine have been fine-tuned following the first publication in the eMagazine in December 2020.

Meanwhile, in deliverable D5.2, the type of content to be incorporated into the eMagazine has been specified, as well as the work process for publishing content in the eMagazine.

Therefore, this deliverable focuses on the evolution of the Community Platform and the eMagazine and how it is currently designed.

During this period, articles have been published in the eMagazine until reaching and surpassing the goal set at the beginning of the project of 48 articles. In the same way, different versions of the eMagazine have been designed until reaching the current one, which will be shown later in this deliverable.

To guarantee the sustainability of the Community Platform, it provides the necessary technical and editorial documentation to manage it, including backup practices, data policy and the final documentation of the legacy of the platform and the content provided by eMagazine.

Within the Content Permanence Policy, we are working to guarantee the continuity of the contents of the website with two different options. The first option is to be taken over, for example, by an interested institution or organization (such as ECSA) to give continuity to the Community Platform and the eMagazine, and the second option would be to maintain a static version of the project to guarantee access to the existing contents from the current URL, as well as a copy of it that would be published in an open repository (Zenodo, for example) for 3 years.

To contextualize the Legacy information and facilitate the operation of the Community Platform in the future, the document offers a historical review of the actions taken to include successive improvements in the Community Platform to contextualize the updates done and the result obtained.

This document updates the information included in deliverables D5.1 and D5.2. Therefore, some sections of the document have been updated with the changes and improvements that we have incorporated during this evolutive process and other sections remain without changes in respect of the previous deliverables.

This document describes the structure and configuration of the channels of communication that configure the Community Platform (the website, the eMagazine, which is the fundamental basis of it, and the Newsletter) and the changes that have been made in them in relation to deliverable D5.2.

It is important to note that, after the publication of this deliverable, no further changes will be made to the structure and functionality of the Community Platform. This is to ensure that the information contained in this document could be used as a guide by anyone who will be managing the website in the future. However, additional eMagazine content will continue to be published until month 38.

To achieve the results documented in this deliverable, the following milestones have been reached. Those mark the evolution and the achievements associated with the launch and operation of the Community platform.

5.1 Launch of Community Platform Site 1 (M5.1). After several adjustments, the website was launched in March 2020, presenting the community platform. The website was structured around the analytical information produced by the various WPs of the project.

5.2. Launch of the Community Platform Site 2 with eMagazine (M5.2). In D.5.2. the eMagazine was incorporated into the Community Platform. Thus, offering relevant information on Citizen Science platforms, reports and initiatives.

5.3. Maintenance and Legacy for Community Platform (M5.3). The aim of this document is to document technical and editorial characteristics of the Community Platform, the website and the eMagazine to guarantee its future operation and maintenance beyond the life span of the CS Track project.

Regarding its structure, this Deliverable D5.3 covers the following aspects:

- Explanation of the improvements and changes made to the website and the CS Track eMagazine with respect to the previous deliverable.
- Review of the articles published in the eMagazine that meet the objectives set out in D.5.1.
- Guide for technical and editorial administration of the Community Platform.

2. Community Platform. Legacy and Final Status Report

2.1. Introduction of Community Platform

The CS Track Website (www.cstrack.eu) is a core element of the Community Platform and the central space where users can access all public information about the project.

The main goal of the website was to create a "Community of Practice that facilitates a two-way channel that allows community members to share the issues that interest them in Citizen Science". In addition to the website, the community of practice could also benefit from getting relevant information via the CS Track newsletter and eMagazine. The website is where all the communication channels of the project are integrated and where the results of the project are shared.

In this sense, the website contains information about the CS Track project and gives access to the rest of the communication channels. Therefore, the communication channels are finally distributed as follows:

Figure 1. Communication channels.

In contrast, the following image shows the old communication channels presented in D5.1. As explained in the following sections, the dashboard has been integrated into the eMagazine:

Figure 2. Old communication channels displayed in D5.1.

This structure and the layout of the website were adjusted to reflect different studies and strategies that are explained later. As explained in the previous deliverables, the

website continues to provide general information about the project and give access to the eMagazine and the Newsletter. In other words, the way in which the communication channels are displayed has changed, but the purpose of the website remains unchanged.

2.2. Legacy

As indicated in the introduction, this deliverable shows the technical features and functionalities of the Community Platform and the e-Magazine.

The publication of the eMagazine has been carried out over a period of 24 months. During this time, the Editorial Committee has been essential for the correct publication of the eMagazine content, and has been in charge of reviewing the entire editorial process. The functions of the Editorial Committee are detailed in deliverable D5.2, as explained in the section of this deliverable dedicated to the Editorial Committee.

Based on the content and characteristics described in deliverables D5.1 and D5.2, it is contemplated that certain aspects of the e-Magazine could change according to the needs. Thus, this document details these changes and explains how it is finally configured.

A process of evolution has been followed, incorporating numerous changes aimed at improving both the Community Platform and, specifically, the eMagazine, in order to improve the communication of results and better connecting with the interests of the different stakeholders.

However, the process of publishing articles in the eMagazine, as explained in D5.2, (using the first publication as an example) has remained the same. Thus, the authors share the article with the URJC team, who arrange to have it reviewed with the EdCom members. Once the revision is completed, the URJC team prepares it in WordPress and announces its publication.

As articles have been published in the eMagazine, technical needs have been adapted, such as the creation of new categories and topics, which are also detailed below.

Finally, E-Magazine scheduling has been modified as content has been published. Initially, it was established to publish two articles per month, however, due to the large flow of articles, more than two articles per month have been published on several occasions. The documentation offered by this Deliverable, both the Legacy and the technical indications for the maintenance of the platform, once the project is finished, offer the fundamental aspects for the sustainability of the Community Platform. This information allows that, once the project and its financing are finished, it can be continued without difficulty by any of the institutions or organizations that work in Europe to promote Citizen Science such as ECSA.

2.2.1. eMagazine articles published during the project

According to the Deliverable D5.1, the CS Track team committed to publishing **48 articles** by the end of the project, that is equivalent to 2 articles per month (no articles were planned for publication during the first year of the project). The first report article, entitled *Evolution of academic publications in citizen science*, was published at the end of December 2020. Since then, a total of **50 articles have been published** and the objective established at the beginning of the project has been achieved. In addition, work is currently underway on more articles to be published in the coming months until the end of the project, which will increase the final number of articles published.

In the following table you can find information about each article, its format and topic:

N	Title	Format	Topic 1	Topic 2	Source	Date of publication
1	Evolution of academic publications in citizen science	Report	Frameworks	Education	Internal	Dec 31, 2020
2	What are the predominant research areas in citizen science projects?	Graphical Article	Formal science	Frameworks	Internal	Mar 1, 2021
3	Reconsidering Citizen Science, a CS Track point of view	Report	Frameworks		Internal	Mar 11, 2021
4	Are citizen science projects multi-disciplinary research activities?	Graphical Article	Frameworks		Internal	Mar 15, 2021
5	Co-creation in Citizen Science explored in Environmental Epidemiology	Report	Frameworks		External	Apr 26, 2021
6	Assessing the impact of citizen science	Report	Impact		External	May 14, 2021
7	CS Track database: first statistical results	Graphical Article	Frameworks		Internal	May 19, 2021
8	Economic considerations in Citizen Science	Report	Frameworks	Impact	Internal	Jun 16, 2021
9	Characterizing engagement in citizen science	Report	Frameworks		Internal	Jun 28, 2021
10	Citizen Science and Open Learning: A Twitter perspective	Graphical Article	Participation	Education	Internal	Jul 1, 2021

11	What technical devices/platforms are used most by Citizen Scientists in their projects?	Graphical Article	Frameworks		Internal	Jul 23, 2021
12	The importance of understanding motivation in Citizen Science projects	Report	Frameworks		External	Jul 26, 2021
13	Survey into Citizen Science Strategies and Initiatives reveals a very mixed picture	Report	Participation	Policy contribution	External	Aug 16, 2021
14	Citizen Science and policy-making – an interview with Linden Farrer from the European Commission	Interview	Policy contribution		Internal	Aug 30, 2021
15	Exploring the impact of a Citizen Science high school project	Report	Impact		External	Sep 3, 2021
16	Characteristics and nature of Citizen Science in Europe today	Report	Frameworks	Formal science	Internal	Sep 15, 2021
17	Who takes part in Citizen Science projects & why?	Briefing report	Frameworks	Participation	Internal	Sep 24, 2021
18	Typical characteristics of citizen science (CS) participants	Graphical Article	Participation		Internal	Sep 29, 2021
19	Using citizen science data to monitor the Sustainable Development Goals: a bottom-up analysis	Report	Policy contribution	Impact	External	Oct 7, 2021
20	Citizen Science and participatory evaluation and impact assessment – an interview with ZSI team in Austria	Interview	Impact	Participation	Internal	Oct 11, 2021
21	Citizen Science and policy-making – an interview with Sven Schade from the JRC	Interview	Policy contribution		Internal	Oct 22, 2021
22	Knowledge building and roles in Citizen Science – findings	Graphical Article	Participation		Internal	Oct 29, 2021

	from the CS Track survey 2021					
23	Citizen Science: Bridging the gap between Formal and Informal Science? – an interview with Romain Julliard from MOSAIC, France	Interview	Formal science		Internal	Nov 2, 2021
24	Increased knowledge generates more positive attitudes to science by citizen science participation	Report	Participation		External	Nov 2, 2021
25	The Formosa Case: A Step Forward on the Acceptance of Citizen-Collected Evidence in Environmental Litigation?	Report	Impact	Policy contribution	External	Nov 3, 2021
26	How do citizen science activities develop and work? Computational analysis techniques can help us find out	Briefing report	Frameworks		Internal	Nov 12, 2021
27	What are the boundaries of citizen science? Learning from a vignette study	Report	Frameworks	Participation	External	Nov 17, 2021
28	Biodiversity citizen science projects: What are the benefits for the participants?	Report	Participation		External	Nov 22, 2021
29	How social network analysis reveals significant variables in Citizen Science projects: the Chimp & See case	Report	Participation		Internal	Nov 26, 2021
30	Why is the protection of online privacy important to the Citizen Science community? – an interview with Huma Shah from CSI-COP	Interview	Education	Participation	Internal	Dec 13, 2021
31	Citizen Science in Schools: Predictors and Outcomes of Participating in	Report	Education	Participation	External	Dec 20, 2021

	Voluntary Political Research					
32	Investigating the potential of citizen science to respond to COVID-19 challenges	Report	Impact	Participation	Internal	Jan 26, 2022
33	How do different participants contribute to the knowledge-building discourse in online citizen science projects?	Graphical Article	Participation		Internal	Feb 7, 2022
34	Questioning the term "citizen science project"	Report	Frameworks		Internal	Feb 11, 2022
35	The use of (not) defining Citizen Science	Report	Frameworks		Internal	Feb 11, 2022
36	12 recommendations for addressing future challenges through citizen science	Briefing Report	Participation		Internal	Feb 25, 2022
37	IMDEA Energy. Communicating science to drive citizen engagement in the transition to a Circular Economy model	Interview	Participation		Internal	Feb 28, 2022
38	More information on replicable models – just one of the priorities for CS Track stakeholders	Report	Participation		Internal	Mar 7, 2022
39	Data donation and Citizen Science – an interview with Elissa Redmiles, Max Planck Institute for Software Systems	Interview	Formal science		Internal	Apr 1, 2022
40	Learning from others – marketing the science and engaging the citizens	Report	Education	Formal science	External	Apr 6, 2022
41	IMDEA's views on Involving Citizens in the Circular Economy	Interview	Frameworks	Formal science	Internal	Apr 29, 2022
42	New models to help us understand patterns of participation in	Briefing report	Participation		Internal	May 4, 2022

	citizen science activities					
43	Expert interviews highlight citizen science benefits, pitfalls and caveats	Briefing report	Frameworks	Impact	Internal	May 25, 2022
44	A short introduction to the CS Track Analytics Workbench	Graphical Article	Frameworks		Internal	May 27, 2022
45	The importance of the few - how a minority of power users shape most of the discourse in CS forums	Graphical Article	Impact		Internal	Jun 17, 2022
46	SDG discussion in the Citizen Science community of Twitter	Graphical Article	Impact		Internal	Jun 24, 2022
47	How is the distribution of tweets for each Sustainable Development Goal inside the Citizen Science community of Twitter?	Graphical Article	Impact		Internal	Jul 8, 2022
48	How does the Citizen Science community use hashtags when discussing e-Health?	Graphical Article	Impact		Internal	Jul 14, 2022
49	Collection of Case Studies of institutional adoption of Citizen Science	Report	Policy contribution		External	Sep 5, 2022
50	What are the most pressing concerns of those working with Citizen Science in a post-pandemic world – an interview with Gitte Kragh	Interview	Frameworks	Impact	Internal	Sep 5, 2022

Figure 3. Articles published in the eMagazine.

Figure 4. Number of articles per format.

Figure 5. Numbers of articles per topic.

Figure 6. Numbers of articles per source.

The following image shows the evolution of the publication of eMagazine articles from January 2021 to September 30, 2022.

Figure 7. Evolution of articles per month.

2.2.2. Evolution and versions of the eMagazine

As indicated in D5.2, the main objective for developing the eMagazine was to present research findings in an accessible and appealing format and to reach target communities. The eMagazine includes articles from the CS Track project and also serves as a platform to share scientific and policy knowledge, to facilitate dialogue between different stakeholders. Regarding its function, it offers relevant information about the project results and key outcomes, as well as recommendations, and provides an interactive platform to exchange knowledge about Citizen Science.

The community platform, through the eMagazine, communicates and shares the project's findings on topics such as:

- Participation patterns.
- Incentives, disincentives, barriers, and enablers.
- Scientific, societal, economic, and democratic benefits.

In the following image we can see how the first version of the eMagazine, within the website, was structured.

Figure 8. How the eMagazine was displayed in the former version of the website.

The main objective of the eMagazine remains the same, that is to share the results of the project and to reach citizen science communities. However, the way the content of the eMagazine is displayed on the website has changed. In the following image, it can be seen how content is currently organised.

Figure 9. How the eMagazine is displayed currently.

Currently, the eMagazine is organised by different topics, but the word "eMagazine" is no longer featured. In other words, there is no button to access the eMagazine, as the front page of the website has in effect become the access to the eMagazine (actually, to its accumulated contents since its launch). Instead, the topics covered in the eMagazine are listed in the menu to give more importance and prominence to the content of the eMagazine and to facilitate easier navigation. The content in the eMagazine is sorted into the following topics:

- Participation & Motivation (Participation)
- Frameworks & Definitions (Frameworks)
- Impact & Reach (Impact)
- Relationship Formal Science (Formal Science)
- Contributing to Policy (Policy-making)
- Education & Learning (Education)

Figure 10. eMagazine topics in the menu.

2.3. Latest improvement actions carried out during the last year

To ensure the impact of the Community Platform we have carried out evaluation activities and used different qualitative techniques. This has made it possible to understand more precisely the interests of the different target groups and to adjust the strategies detailed below.

2.3.1. Focus Group and UX Research

A study was conducted in September 2021 to improve the user experience (UX). This study consisted of a series of Focus Groups in which over 30 participants gave us feedback about their experience of the website. The purpose of these focus groups was to assess the extent to which both the content and the format of the communication efforts led by URJC and ATiI in CS Track meet the needs and expectations of our target stakeholders' groups.

WP6 published a report explaining the whole process and results of the focus groups (<https://cstrack.eu/format/reports/more-information-on-replicable-models-just-one-of-the-priorities-for-CS-Track-stakeholders/>).

As a result of these discussions, opportunities to improve website usability were identified and acted upon.

2.3.2. External Advisory Board (EAB)

The CS Track External Advisory Board is made up of external experts from institutions involved in Citizen Science activities as well as informal and lifelong science learning, industry, education, research, NGOs, and the public sector. The current membership is made up of scientific experts from different disciplines and geographical areas.

The main task of the external advisory board is to advise on different aspects of our work including our research and analytical activities, the tools and resources we are developing to provide insight into the nature, value and orientation of Citizen Science and, most especially, the extent to which the project can have a significant impact in keeping with its mission and values.

The External Advisory Board has met in two opportunities and provided valuable and critical input to the project in both formal and informal settings. Their recommendations have helped the CS Track team improve the impact and usability of the Community Platform. In the last EAB report of April 2022, the evolution of the Community Platform has been very positively commented upon.

2.4. The eMagazine

The eMagazine is one of the most important communication channels of the project and an essential part of the Community Platform. This deliverable explains how the eMagazine is finally configured and what changes have been made with respect to D5.2. Therefore, this document reflects the definitive version of the eMagazine.

As described in the former versions of Deliverable D5.1 and Deliverable D5.2, the eMagazine is an electronic magazine that includes articles with advanced visualization as a specific type of post prepared by the project's experts. It communicates interesting findings gathered through our analytics and other studies.

Since the launch of the eMagazine, adjustments have been continuously made to improve the presentation of the contents. As with the former deliverable, the changes that the eMagazine has undergone since the publication of D5.2 are explained in the following paragraphs.

2.4.1. How the eMagazine articles are displayed on the homepage

The way the eMagazine's latest articles are displayed has also changed since the previous update of the website. Currently, and from now on, the latest outputs will be displayed on the homepage as follows.

In the following images you can see the difference between how the eMagazine's content was displayed and how it is currently presented.

<https://old.citizenscience.eu/sub/2022-04/633811/https://old.citizenscience.eu/>

Figure 11. How the eMagazine previously displayed.

Figure 12. How the eMagazine's content is displayed in the homepage currently.

The most recent output is displayed in the centre of the page, while the titles of the four articles preceding it appear in a column on the right-hand of the page. On the left hand side, the latest News & Events outputs are displayed in the blue column.

Scrolling down the page, each article is displayed under the assigned topic:

Figure 13. Outputs in the Participation & Motivation topic.

Figure 14. Outputs in the Frameworks & Definitions topic.

2.4.2. Classification of eMagazine's articles

eMagazine articles are divided into different categories, namely:

- **Format.** In this category, with respect to the last deliverable, where it was indicated that there were two different types of outputs (reports and

graphical articles), two more types of outputs (briefing reports and interviews) have been added in order to expand the content of the eMagazine.

- o **Graphical article.** these are articles that provide graphic information synthetically and show the data stored in the database of CS Track project to the users. An example is shown in the following image:

Figure 15. Graphical article example.

- o **Report.** This category includes articles with analyses carried out by the CS Track project. Comments are enabled so that users can ask any questions about the topic. An example is shown in the next image.

Figure 16. Report article example.

- o **Briefing report.** These articles are summaries of selected public CS Track project's deliverables and adapted to the article format. Report category and Briefing report subcategory have to be selected in order to publish articles under this category:

Search Categories

Interview

News

Opinion

Reports

Briefing report

Webinars

Source

Figure 17. Categories to select in WordPress to publish a briefing report.

Expert interviews highlight citizen science benefits, pitfalls and caveats

BY EDITORIAL TEAM | MAY 23, 2022

Building Trust in Science

The CS Trust research team, led by partners Christine Britton and Michael Heine from the Waterburyville Water - Science Shop Vermont, has published a report called *Overweight Citizens for Healthy Kids*, the document builds on the preceding expert interviews. Christy Britton says the conceptual foundations for the project, the document maps citizen science landscapes in the European continent beyond funding programmes, policies, advisory and working groups, and opportunities for participating in citizen science activities. However, the report presents an overview of additional citizen science activities in sectors that complement the previously published literature related to citizen science activities in education. This document also includes interviews with Allison, Anna, Harpreet and Anushka experts in citizen science, research ethics and open knowledge, which outline main findings. Interviews are included in the *Overweight Citizens for Healthy Kids* report and are in the focus of this article.

Interviews with experts

The CS Trust research team interviewed experts who live or work on different continents to have citizen out projects which help under the European Commission's initiative of citizen science in different parts of the world. When selecting experts, the interviewers considered several dimensions: geography, professional status and background, sufficient ability in their field to give an opinion to those who are often called in research on citizen science, and scientific expertise in respect to the topic of the interview. *Overweight for Healthy Kids* reports were developed and 12 of them were interviewed.

Benefits, pitfalls and caveats

Experts shared their thoughts on some potential benefits, pitfalls and caveats of citizen science, here are some of their observations:

- Lyn Heine** (University of Cape Town, South Africa) believes that greater citizen science can provide *counter expertise* and open access to data powerful people with hidden agendas try to hide. However, activists and scientists should be careful not to overstep their role of expertise.
- Anna Harpreet** (University of Cambridge, UK) believes that open access to knowledge in citizen science is a potential *irreversible loss of findings* for *important citizen expertise*.
- Harve Thomsen-Björk** (University of Copenhagen, Denmark) says that "understanding the experts' worldview in citizen science projects may cause *unintentional abuse* between it causes and how the future, reciprocal and iterative" the project is to conduct.

- "It does not work for all kinds of research." **Sara Decoster** (KU Leuven, Belgium)
- "Successful citizen science is very time consuming." **Alena Quinn** (University of Idaho, USA)
- "If the citizen science work is in the broader community, it's more likely to get a lot of support or even a collective challenge these days, they want you to have some component of interacting with the community and they want the phrase citizen science to be on your resume. Also, having to do a push in the way that it might take resources away from other activities, it might overlap the coverage of other science." **Alena Quinn**
- "There are two potential that scientists might miss out on something by partially outsourcing data collection to volunteers. For projects scientists would not be doing something in data collection that citizens would not. The opportunity for unregulated findings to be collected." **Sara Decoster**
- "Scientists need to remain unbiased, quality assurance is necessary. (but we can't do that either)." **Sara Decoster**
- "Citizen science is just a building block in their science. It is a problem if anything can be called citizen science." **Alexander Britton, Denmark**
- "I think people need to realize that an important aspect of science is about *what kind of university*, which one is not essential components of science, or demonstrated by epistemologists like Popper & Kuhn. The idea that something is true only until the contrary has been proven, but how often are asking scientists to give other answers, to say them the truth and one not always aware that the truth might not exist or that we have no authority to not the truth of tomorrow." **Sara Decoster**

Ethical issues

The experts in research ethics and research integrity mentioned several ethical issues, including informed consent, privacy, and inclusion/exclusion and some that are not widely discussed in citizen science communities.

- ethical issues may also depend on project design. "The ethical project objectives, method, data availability and distribution in which the project operates" also **Harve Thomsen-Björk** is "such decisions about ethical issues in a responsible (in participatory research activity) such as participatory and reciprocal monitoring."
- Recognition of the citizens' involvement of citizen science that it remains *citizen science*. For example, scientific journals may be difficult to accept quality *citizen science*.
- Without payment, people with low financial resources can be excluded from participating, especially when it comes to low low-income contributions.

How to mitigate ethical issues?

Interviewed experts shared their suggestions of how some of the ethical issues can be mitigated, including:

- Alena Quinn** suggested that closer cooperation between scientists and citizen scientists can help prevent ethical issues, but even a closed ethical issue scientists are not aware of.
- Harve Thomsen-Björk** recommends making data collection as low-tech as possible and to give open access to the knowledge of the data.
- Robbeet Leve** (Maastricht University, Maastricht, The Netherlands) believes that data and results may be made available to citizens in an understandable way.

Figure 18. Report briefing report example.

The authors of deliverables collaborate with the editorial team to produce briefing reports.

- Interview.** Interviews with experts in the field of citizen science have been conducted to enrich the eMagazine. The topics of these interviews are related to the main topics of the project. Some of them were text-based only, and some were video interviews that were later transcribed. Like the briefing reports, the interviews always carry the stamp of "Project results". In this case, it is indicated who the authors are, that is who conducted the interviews.

IMDEA's views on Involving Citizens in the Circular Economy

BY MANUEL GÉRTRUDIX BARRIO, ALEJANDRO CARBONELL ALCOCER, JUAN ROMERO LUIS AND ALBERTO SÁNCHEZ ACEDO | APR 29, 2022 | FRAMEWORKS & DEFINITIONS, INTERNAL CONTENT, INTERVIEW, RELATIONSHIP WITH FORMAL SCIENCE

Figure 19. Interview performed by WP5.

Citizen Science: Bridging the gap between Formal and Informal Science? – an interview with Romain Julliard from MOSAIC, France

BY SALLY REYNOLDS | NOV 2, 2021

Figure 20. Interview performed by WP6.

IMDEA's views on Involving Citizens in the Circular Economy

BY MANUEL HERRERO, ALBERTO SANCHEZ AGUIRRE, ALBA ROMERO LUIS AND ALBERTO SANCHEZ AGUIRRE (APR 29, 2022) | FRAMEWORKS & DEFINITIONS, INTERNAL CONTENT, INTERVIEW, RELATIONSHIP WITH FORMAL SCIENCE

Reading time: 7 minutes

Jose Luis is the head of the Systems Unit and Lorena Morán is responsible for communication and Image of IMDEA Energy in Spain. The project at IMDEA focused research on the focus on determining the sustainability of any energy system, its sustainability, its cost, its energy, not only environmental, but also economic and social. It aims to be developing energy systems that are environmentally sustainable, but also socially responsible, and the involvement of the public is essential in this regard. As about future projects, we will continue progress if we do not fall into progress, and in the end, citizen involvement means based on the top principles described by the European Citizen Science Association as a fundamental driving force.

You speak with them to test if their research aims of high excellence agree with this process of social dialogue in science and technology, and how they propose citizen participation in scientific research processes, based on participation in projects related to the Circular Economy, such as the E3C network, whose objective is to promote the Urban Laboratory.

Manual Herrero: What role should citizen science play in connecting society with scientific research?

Jose Luis: Without a doubt, it is a fundamental role. Research cannot be based on society if it is not fully aligned to society's needs, especially on the part of those who work in the public sector. We need the process of identification, transparency and, above all, communication between the two spheres: society and researchers. But we also need to understand how we can involve citizens actively in the scientific process so that they can better understand, directly, the role we play in scientific and technological development.

Research cannot turn its back on society. It is essential to respond to society's needs, especially on the part of those of us who work in the public sector.

Man: What are the main challenges we face, in the short and medium term, to develop the transition to a circular economy?

JL: The circular economy is more than recycling waste or reusing water. It is a real transformation of the economy. We have to create a new economic model which different processes compete. It is a transformation of the way of producing, which affects the economy. But it is also a great transformation because we have to produce more by consuming or using fewer and producing less waste products. So, the more we get citizens involved, the more we can make to get the economy involved in any part of the process, because we will be able to change and the faster we can achieve the transition to the circular economy.

Man: How do you think citizen science helps drive the transition to a circular economy itself? What are the keys to encouraging this process through citizen involvement?

JL: As I was saying, it is undoubtedly an essential role because society must be aware of and involved in the circular economy and its development. Research must be able to bring the advantages of accepting these by-products or innovative ideas in the circular economy offering mechanisms for them to participate in its different processes. This involves the transfer of knowledge and concepts, and the necessary collaboration, via expertise for the effective implementation of the circular economy in our society.

Society must be aware of and involved in the circular economy and its development.

Man: How can this process be encouraged in schools? If you have created out-of-school or carrying out experiences of this nature, participation or communication aimed at young people and school teachers, can you tell us something about these experiences if any, and you think they should be generalised? In what way?

JL: It includes the children and young people as well as any equipment and facilities that we need. We are focused more on trying to create a way to involve society in the economy and involve them in scientific and technological processes. At IMDEA Energy we are very active in the transfer process. Every year we hold activities during European Week where we have aimed at a balance between the open night and events, where we tell them about our activities in a fun way. We propose a series of activities and games so that school children participate, understand the scientific concepts on which our research is based (and understand how they can be part of the process of change, participating in different projects and others in which that involvement is essential).

We are also often involved on a personal basis, for example when participating in activities at schools to show students my research and see energy developments. The aim is for these children to know what the reality will be when they reach adulthood and what options they have to get involved in research and technological development processes.

These are activities whose main objective is to involve students in the processes of scientific research, so that children and teenagers know not only their results but also the ways to participate and contribute to research.

Lorena Morán: As Jose Luis was saying, at IMDEA Energy we participate in several scientific culture activities in the framework of the "Innovation Council of the Community of Madrid". For example, the Citizen Lab Network, where we, the European Researcher's Night, the International Day of Women and Girls in Science 2022, and the Madrid Science Fair, within the framework of the E3C network, whose main objective is to involve citizens in the processes of scientific research, in their own words and through their own results but also the ways to participate and contribute to research. This involves awareness and involvement, and generates attention with the scientific sector, allowing scientific activities. I think that the main objective we achieved in the last week, is generate the attention for the professional and academic development of students and, on the other hand, to raise social awareness to get involved in scientific and technological developments and to understand them as a daily sign, the relevance will be for progress to reach such sustainability as the transition to the circular economy.

Man: What role do you think citizen communication and popularisation should play to improve public support and involvement in the transition to a circular economy?

JL: Scientific communication is the basic tool for these concepts to reach society and for scientists/researchers themselves do not know how to communicate and so that they reach society and can be really understood by anyone. But we have to reach every citizen who is interested in this topic or who wants to know in a general way, what the process regarding the hydrogen economy or any other matter involves. Citizen involvement and participation means taking advantage of all the possibilities offered by scientific communication.

Man: You, that is right, I think that citizen communication is fundamental nowadays, the less in a world in which what is not being understood probably does not exist, and sometimes science tends to be too focused on the field and does not reach the general public. In order to actively involve them, it is essential to make scientific developments in sustainability and green transition accessible. We need to make citizens, both young and old, aware of what is being done, of the relevance of scientific developments in their daily lives. But we also need to communicate by involving them, to make them feel that they can be part of its development and to show them the ways to do it. We have to improve social awareness and generate ideas and synergies that make scientifically diverse scientific research, but also involve them in the process of social transformation through science.

Audiovisual Content

Duration: 03:00 | Fully featured | Researchers

Categories: | Frameworks & Definitions | Internal Content | Interview | Relationship with Formal Science

Figure 21. Interview article example.

- **Topic.** This has been the main change made to the eMagazine categories. This category allows authors to assign one or more topics to eMagazine articles.
 - o **Participation & Motivation (Participation)**
 - o **Frameworks & Definitions (Frameworks)**
 - o **Impact & Reach (Impact)**
 - o **Relationship Formal Science (Formal Science)**
 - o **Contributing to Policy (Policy-making)**

o **Education & Learning (Education)**

- **Source.** This new category helps readers identify whether eMagazine content is produced by the CS Track team members or external researchers/experts:
 - o **Internal.** Articles written by members of the CS Track group and are results of the project. To differentiate them from external content, these articles carry a distinctive stamp added to the featured images.

Figure 22. Stamp indicating “Project result”.

Figure 23. Some examples of internal outputs with the stamp. From left to right above: report and interview. Below: graphical articles.

- o **External.** To enrich the eMagazine and encourage the sharing of knowledge on citizen science, external experts are invited to

contribute articles. In this way, complementary viewpoints on the results of the CS Track project are provided. Unlike internal articles, external outputs are not stamped.

In addition, as mentioned in the previous deliverables, all articles include information indicating the main and secondary target group(s) to which they are aimed based on those identified in Deliverable 5.1.

By means of an active tagging system (tags and categories), readers can find out the target audience, as well as navigate directly to other articles aimed at the same audience.

These categories can be expanded and as many audiences can be added as desired:

- Academics
- Citizen Scientist
- Company representative
- CS Platforms
- CS project initiator/founder
- Educators
- NGO
- Organisational representative
- Policy-maker
- Researchers

Audience: [Citizen Scientist](#) | [CS project initiator/founder](#)

Categories: [Frameworks & Definitions](#) | [Graphical article](#) | [Internal Content](#)

Figure 24. An example of how these categories are shown at the bottom of each article.

2.4.3. Structure and content description

Articles for the eMagazine are edited in the default WordPress editor. The structure of these articles is shown below:

2.4.3.1. Report and Briefing Report structure

Figure 25. This is the main structure of a Report Article and Briefing Report Article. More Headers and Texts might be added in case they are required.

2.4.3.2. Graphical Article structure

Figure 26. This is the main structure of a Graphical Article. More Headers and Texts might be added in case they are required.

2.4.3.3. Interview structure

Figure 27. This is the main structure of an Interview. The last header (Additional information) is optional.

2.5. Newsletter

As in the past, users can also subscribe to the CS Track newsletter to stay informed about project updates or general citizen science news, events, reports and articles.

The newsletter has been published monthly, containing all the outputs of the eMagazine published in that month. The newsletter has been sent through Mailchimp, and once it has been sent, it is added to the website and can be found under the Newsletter tab.

Figure 28. Newsletter page.

Users have to subscribe to receive the newsletter, .

The monthly content of the Newsletter includes information on:

- News and events from CS track project.
- Content published in eMagazine (reports and technical products and citizen science)
- Curated information that will not be suitable to be published in News and events section (published on Twitter).

2.6. Analytics of use and participation of the CS Community

Since the beginning, the web of Community Platform and the eMagazine has been monitored through an analytics system with the aim of evaluating and improving its use and participation.

Below we show two representative graphs of the web analytics corresponding to two different periods of the project, each divided into 15 months. The first one corresponds to the period from the beginning of the platform until May 31, 2021. The second graph corresponds to the period from June 1, 2021 to September 2022.

Figure 29. Analytics March 2020-May 2021.

Figure 30. Analytics June 2021-Sept 2022.

Comparing both graphs, there has been a notable increase in the number of users and visits to the website, as well as the session duration, which has increased by almost one minute. In addition, the bounce rate has dropped, which is significant in terms of the interest of users entering the website. The evolution of these values projects an upward trend for the platform.

On the other hand, the participation of the citizen science community in the Community Platform has been a fundamental objective of the CS Track project. To encourage this participation, the project has offered several channels that include:

social media (Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube) and a powerful comment system in the Community Platform and the eMagazine.

Among social media channels, Twitter has been the most successful in terms of engagement and audience, with more than 1000 followers and more than 1500 tweets and a daily activity with great impact on the audience. For example, the following image shows a pinned tweet in which there are great values in terms of retweets and likes.

Figure 31. Pinned tweet.

The system allows several functions such as adding inline commenting and feedback; commenting on post content; live notification with real-time updating; making social comments and rating posts directly on rating stars; etc.

After this period of launching the Community Platform, readers have the opportunity to interact in the comments section. In this way, feedback from the audience can be obtained. In several articles, readers have added comments giving their opinion on the article, receiving feedback from the authors themselves.

This commenting system will be used for reports, using a comment plugin for WordPress named *wpDiscuz*. Thus, if a reader is interested in a piece of information or needs to go into detail about the report, he/she can ask a question, which will be passed to and answered by the author.

The steps for using this comment system are the following:

1. Someone asks a question in the report, getting pending for approval by the administrator of the website.
2. The administrator of the website receives an email asking for his/her approval of the comment.
3. Once the comment is approved to appear in the report, the person who asked receives a mail to subscribe for new comments on our website. He/she can confirm his/her subscription or cancel it.

The following images detail the information necessary to make a comment on a report. It is necessary to fill in the name, email and check the reCAPTCHA.

Figure 32. Feedback form.

In addition, it is possible to make a rating of the report. The readers can vote and give a rating to the article by stars, as shown below:

Figure 33. Article Rating.

The following image explains in more detail the options for including comments.

eMagazine

Some options that we can enable for the Community Platform

- Inline Questions and Feedback
- Comment Bubble
- Post Rating
- Social Commenting
- Google reCAPTCHA

Figure 34. Explanation of the comment system.

A first evaluation of the use of the Community Platform and eMagazine, and of participation in the project, shows an upward trend in terms of audience and interest in the platform's contents, as well as the time spent by users on the platform.

Regarding the participation system, it should be noted that Twitter has obtained great participation from the audience and followers of the project, but the system of direct participation in the Community Platform and the eMagazine, offers modest results in the level of interaction through the comments' system, as well as in the extent of rating the articles published in the eMagazine. This aspect, which was addressed in the focus groups conducted, may be since, although the content is valuable and useful for the different stakeholders of the project, it does not imply that they require a direct interaction process through this channel, which raises the opportunity to rethink the interaction model through this procedure.

3. Maintenance and documentation to back-up practices and data policy

3.1. Technical Features

The Community Platform works in the form of a website available from the domain <https://cstrack.eu/>

This section explains, first, how the technology environment is set up for its operation and maintenance, and secondly, which are the publication processes to know how to continue working on new articles and publications.

The legacy documentation of the Community Platform is composed of:

- This document with all the necessary information about maintenance and operation of Community Platform.
- Links to backups of:
 - Web backup (Files and database)
 - Newsletter backup (Mailchimp)

3.1.1. WordPress

The website is managed on WordPress and has been developed by WP5 in coordination with WP6 during the project. The current version of WordPress running is 6.0.

Annex 2 shows a guide to accessing WordPress and how to work on the platform.

3.1.1.1. *Creative Commons Licence*

To facilitate the reuse and maximum dissemination of the content, the "Creative Commons" plugin has been included, which licenses the content with a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

The license is included in all content published by default in the HTML metadata, to facilitate retrieval by search engines in readable machine format, and is included visually in the footer of the Community Platform.

3.1.2. Newsletter

The newsletter has been published monthly. For this purpose, it has been managed in Mailchimp. On this platform, communication campaigns on project results are created and sent to subscribers by automated e-mails.

In the following image, the Mailchimp interface is shown. In the "Campaigns tab", the newsletter for each month is created.

Figure 35. Mailchimp dashboard.

Here are all the monthly newsletter campaigns. To create a new one, the last one is replicated:

Figure 36. Replicate a campaign.

Annex 3 explains how to create a campaign in Mailchimp and how to publish it on the web using WordPress.

3.1.3. Backups policy

Backup management is carried out according to the following policies and technical criteria:

- For the management of backups of the Community Platform, the UpdraftPlus WordPress Backup Plugin is used.
- An automatic weekly file backup and a daily database backup are performed. The last two backup copies of the files and the last four of the databases are kept.
- The plugins and themes are also saved in the file backup, in addition to the files.

- The backups are stored, via FTP, on another server other than the production one, so a second location is used for security.
- The database copy is encrypted by security policy.

The backup of the final version of the Community Platform is also available in Zenodo, at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7071573>

In addition, a backup of the Newsletter management system (Mailchimp) has been made, which includes the campaigns, the audience, the reports, the templates of the newsletter and the Gallery. This backup includes the data in CSV, which would allow the newsletter system to be restored both in Mailchimp and in other services, such as Sendiblu or similar, with some minor adaptation.

3.1.4. Data policy

3.1.4.1. Privacy Policy and Security procedures

The privacy policy and the security procedures will be in accordance with the deliverable D8.2. POPD – Requirement No. 3 elaborated in WP 8 and already delivered on 15.3.20. This deliverable details the Personal Data Protection procedures, specifically regarding the data collection, storage, analysis or other handling for any purpose associated with the research carried out in the CS Track project. In addition, this deliverable includes The POPD strategy/mechanism being implemented in the project detailing: a) the Data Protection Regulation on the treatment of data, b) the Prerequisites for approval by the DPO (Data Protection Officer) for the treatment of personal data in the frame of a research project; c) the personal data protection regulations governing photos and videos; and d) the Plan of action in case of a Digital Privacy Violation. As far as security procedures are concerned, it states that "All data collected on portable devices will be encrypted and transferred to secure storage facilities at the earliest opportunity. Data will be stored on secure servers with regular backup." (p. 7) Both the dashboard and the eMagazine will show only interpretations based on aggregated data sets that are no longer associated with individuals. Access to the data will comply with the data security and ethical aspects described in sections 4 and 5 of the deliverable D7.1 Data Management Plan.

3.1.4.2. Cookies policy

The privacy and cookie policy are implemented according to the Privacy Policy and Security procedures explained above. For the preparation of the cookie policy, the following have been used: a) the European recommendations on the use of cookies published by GDPR.eu (2020), b) the template of the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD, 2020) based on these European recommendations.

The full text of the Cookies' policy to be included in the platform is available in Annex 4 and 5.

3.1.5. Project sustainability

We are working to ensure the continuity of the web content. To achieve this, two different scenarios are presented:

In the first option, the platform would be taken over by an institution or organization that is interested in the contents and can increase these beyond the end of the project, so we are currently working with organizations such as ECSA that may be interested. If they are indeed interested in giving continuity to the Community Platform and the eMagazine, we will study the best way to move forward formally, either in the current system or by integrating the Community Platform into their own project. This scenario would guarantee the continuity of the content, its updating and the technical solution developed. In addition, by delivering this document, the necessary information and resources are provided for them to do so.

If, for any reason, this first option will not be feasible, we will opt for the short-term sustainability, for 3 years, of the hosting and domain by URJC or ATIT, either in a dynamic or static version. If a static version is created that does not require maintenance, we would indicate the period in which the project was active, a statement that the project has ended, and provide further details on who to contact in case of new queries. In addition, it would be published in a public repository or subdomain, to ensure access to existing content at the end of the project.

In both cases, a complete backup of the entire installation (files and database) would be left linked from Zenodo so that, at any time, the project and all its contents can be migrated, recovered or installed.

3.2. Editorial Features

According to deliverable D5.2, where the editorial process was explained, this deliverable consolidates the fact that work has continued in this way. The editorial process as explained in D5.2 is explained below.

The editorial process comprises all the steps from the moment an author sends the content to the editors until it is published. The process is the same independently of the type of content involved.

Following the delivery of Deliverable 5.1 we have been working on improving the process to carry out the review by the editorial committee, editors, and authors. It is described in detail below.

3.2.1. Editorial Guidelines

The publication of content in the eMagazine and, in general, on the Community Platform website has followed the following editorial guidelines.

3.2.1.1. Editorial standards and Style guide

To ensure the best text editing work for our eMagazine, the Editorial Guidelines of the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) will be used; there are available in <https://www.bbc.com/editorialguidelines>

Likewise, the BBC style guide <https://www.bbc.co.uk/newsstyleguide> is also followed; this guide details many of the rules of spelling, punctuation and grammar, as well as issues of accuracy, fairness and impartiality.

3.2.1.2. Gender considerations

In the analysis of users of the platform done in Deliverable 5.1, the gender perspective has been evaluated.

The ethical and gender requirements established in the CS Track project and, specifically, those established in Deliverable 8.1, are followed in the writing and editing of the articles.

As well, the recommendations of the European Portal [GenPORT](#) (European Union, 2014) are followed, which provides information about gender and science to publish material, reports or articles.

Further, the stereotypes related to sex and gender are considered when generating ideas to rethink language (word choice, metaphors, analogies, and naming practices) and visual representations (images, tables, and graphs) as it is suggested in [Gendered Innovations How Gender Analysis Contributes to Research, European Commission](#) (Schiebinger, 2013) and in [Gender-responsive communications toolkit](#) (IOM, 2020)

These gender considerations have also been taken into account in the preparation of eMagazine's publications. In this sense, 34% of eMagazine articles are authored by women (one or more), 24% by men (one or more) and 42% by both men and women (both).

The following graph shows the ratio of publications by gender in terms of authorship:

Figure 37. Distribution of the 50 articles by gender.

Finally, a total of 9 interviews were carried out. In 44.44% of the interviews, the interviewees were women (one or more), in 33.33% were men (one or more) and in 22.22% included interviewees of both genders.

Figure 38. Distribution of interviewees by gender.

3.2.1.3. Ethical considerations

In the requirements' specification for the community platform detailed in Deliverable 5.1 it was established that the data collected from registered and non-registered users of the CS TRACK project will fall within the scope of the standard operation of research projects funded under H2020.

Also, that access to the data will comply with the data security and ethical aspects described in sections 4 and 5 of Deliverable D7.1 - Data Management Plan.

In the implementation of the eMagazine we have followed the principles of information law and consent. According to the General Data Protection Regulation (RGPD). (UE 2016/679) all personal data are stored securely.

The mitigation measures undertaken include providing visibility to privacy and cookies policy within the website of the CS Track project <https://cstrack.eu/privacy-cookies-policy/>

The data stored will be the following: username, the name and surname, and email. Other information required, if at all, will be provided (or not) on a voluntary basis. In the case of users without registration, personal details are not registered. In these cases, only the information related to cookies detailed in Deliverable 5.1 is stored.

3.2.2. Agents' Roles in the Editorial Process

3.2.2.1. *Author*

- The author is the researcher who writes the article and the person in charge of the content included in the article.
- Once it is finished, the author should send his/her proposal to a colleague/s from the same WP to review it. It will be the first review of the article, concentrating on content aspects (see the eMagazine publication checklist).
- When the internal review is completed, the author will send the article to the multimedia editor.
- The author should be in touch with his/her colleague/s, the multimedia editor, and the editorial committee.

3.2.2.2. *Multimedia editor*

- The URJC team performs the work of the multimedia editor.
- The multimedia editor will be responsible to review the content on the second step, both in content and formal aspects (see the eMagazine publication checklist).
- They will adapt the content as needed, create the media and publish a draft of the post. This draft is shared with all people involved in the review process: editorial committee, author/s and multimedia editor.
- To the extent needed, the multimedia editor will be in contact with the author and the editorial committee.

3.2.2.3. *External Collaborator*

- Researchers and external experts to CS Track project that have been invited to collaborate in the eMagazine.
- Any member of the CS Track project may propose to the Editorial Committee an external collaborator. The Editorial Committee must approve this proposition before continuing with the process.
- Upon approval, the external collaborator becomes an author, taking part in the review process in a comparable manner to that of authors that are members of the project. His/her contribution will be supervised by the member who invited him/her to contribute.
- His/her function consists of doing the first review of the article content following the indications shown in the eMagazine's checklist for publications.

- This person is expected to be very knowledgeable on the topic.
- He/she and the author are expected to be in regular contact with each other while the article is under consideration..

The following scheme summarizes the different agents and their functions in the internal editorial process.

Figure 39. Outline of the editorial process for publications by project authors.

This other scheme details the different agents and their functions in the external editorial process.

Figure 40. Editorial process outline for guest author publications.

3.2.2.4. Editorial Committee (EdCom)

The editorial committee is the expert group in charge of reviewing the articles proposed by other members of the project for their correct publication.

Once the project has ended, this system based on the current management by an Editorial Committee will no longer be used. However, the process is described below in case there is the possibility of adopting a similar approach in the future.

It is necessary to explain that the members of the Editorial Committee are experts in the field of Citizen Science. If it were not possible to work with an expert group, this team could be replaced by the figure of an editor-in-chief.

The Editorial Committee is the body approved by the consortium to carry out the prior editorial review of the contents that are published in the eMagazine. It has been set prior to the first publication of the eMagazine.

Deliverable D5.2 fully describes the organization and functions of the EdCom, as well as the editorial workflow and the editorial process. For a detailed understanding of the process, it is recommended to review the D5.2 document. The following is only a description of the work process followed by EdCom during this period.

EdCom members meet for one hour the first week of each month to review the articles to be published during that month. Decisions are made for publication and the status of the publication is reviewed, prioritizing the content. Once an agreement is reached among all members, the article is ready to be designed and published on WordPress.

Before each meeting, the team formed by the URJC sends by e-mail to the rest of the EdCom members the points to be discussed in each meeting. Once the meeting is over, an email is sent again summarizing the points discussed, the objectives achieved and the decisions taken.

The review time for each article depends on its complexity, ease of understanding of the content and the comments and suggestions made by the EdCom members.

4. References

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5. Annexes

5.1. Annex 1: How to work on WordPress

To access the WordPress dashboard where all the contents of the website are managed, it is necessary to have previous access, which is granted by the administrators. Once you have this access you must go to the following link: <https://cstrack.eu/ciberlogin> and enter the required data.

The image shows a WordPress login page. At the top center is the WordPress logo. Below it is a white login form with a blue border. The form contains two input fields: 'Username or Email Address' and 'Password'. The password field has a small eye icon to its right. Below the password field is a checkbox labeled 'Remember Me' and a blue 'Log In' button. Underneath the form, there is a link for 'Lost your password?' and a link that says 'Go to Citizen Science | CS Track Project'. At the bottom of the form area, there is a link for 'Privacy & Cookies Policy'. At the very bottom of the page, there is a language selector showing 'English (UK)' with a dropdown arrow and a 'Change' button.

Figure 41. Page to access the WordPress dashboard.

Once inside, this is the dashboard that you will find:

Figure 42. WordPress dashboard.

All the content of the web is managed from here.

In the right column are the tabs “Posts” and “Pages”. In these tabs, we can manage the eMagazine articles and the pages that make up the website, respectively.

In addition, there are other tabs allowing access to the WordPress configuration.

It is important to note that the eMagazine articles (posts) are edited with the default WordPress editor, while the pages are edited with the Divi Builder plugin.

5.1.1. Posts tab

The “Posts” tab contains all the items of the eMagazine. To publish a new item, click on the “Add new” button and edit it with the default editor, not with Divi Builder.

Figure 43. Post tab to publish a new post.

When publishing a new post, in the left column you can find all the features of that post. Among them are:

- **Categories**

- o Format:

- Events
 - CS Track events
 - Graphical article
 - Interview
 - News
 - Opinion
 - Reports
 - Briefing report
 - Webinars

- o Source:

- External content
 - Internal content

- o **Topic.** The new eMagazine categories:

- Contribution to Policy-Making
 - Education & Learning
 - Frameworks & Definitions
 - Impact & Reach
 - Participation & Motivation
 - Relationship with Formal Science

- o Status:

- Highlighted

- o **Test.** These categories are used to see the result of the articles without displaying them on the web. The objective is to perform the necessary tests before making the output public:

- Beta Graphical article
 - Beta Interview
 - Beta Opinion

- Beta Report
 - Beta briefing report
- SUX

As you can see, there are more categories that do not belong to eMagazine. Therefore, in "Posts" tab you can create other content such as news and opinion items, apart from the content of the eMagazine itself.

- **Excerpt.** A summary of the article of approximately 60 words is written here.
- **Featured image.** Here, you add an image that will identify the article on the web. Depending on whether it is an internal or external output, the image will be stamped or not.
- **Discussion.** "Allow comments" must be selected in all articles except Graphical articles.

Figure 44. Discussion tab to allow comments.

- **Tags.** This section is to indicate the target or audience for each of the articles published:
 - Academics
 - Citizen Scientist
 - Company representative
 - CS Platforms
 - CS project initiator/founder
 - Educators
 - NGO
 - Organisational representative
 - Policy-maker
 - Researchers

However, you can add as many tags as you want.

- **Authors.** The authors are most of the members of the CS Track project who have contributed to the website. However, if it is necessary to add a new author, it is possible to do it from this tab.

5.1.2. Pages Tab

In “Pages” tab are all the pages that make up the website. All the pages are built with Divi Builder.

In bold the pages shown on the web, and in italics the ones that are in draft:

- **About**
- **Contact us**
- CS
- CS Track project (QR). No index.
- Dashboard eMagazine. No index
- *Demo Dashboard*
- *EMagazine*
- *EMagazine-old*
- **External Advisory Board**
- *Glossary*
- **Home**
- *Home old*
- **News & Events**
- **Newsletter**
- *Newsletter (Draft)*
- **Privacy & Cookies Policy**
- **Publications**
- *Publications_old*
- **Subscribe to our newsletter**
- *SUX0 Welcome 0.* No index. This page was used only for the Focus group UX study.

5.1.3. Translate content

Although the platform and its contents are in English, to make it easier for Citizen Science communities that speak other languages to access content translated into their language, an automatic translation system with GTranslate has been included in the top menu to facilitate access in the most widely spoken languages.

Figure 45. Plugin GTranslate to multilingual content.

5.1.4. Metadata

To ensure the success of the platform, a metadata management system has been included. This allows to maximize the findability and recoverability of the contents published in the eMagazine. Also, to ensure that the community of interest in Citizen Science can locate these quickly, whether they know the CS Track project and want to access material from the project's channels or they found content through external search.

To improve SEO (Search Engine Optimization) a plugin has been incorporated to facilitate the management of both the eMagazine globally and each of the published articles.

At a general level, the settings for titles and meta tags, taxonomies, files, etc., have been optimized; the XML sitemap, the image sitemap and the HTML sitemap of the site have been created. Analytics tracking system using Google Analytics has also been included to evaluate the use made by readers and incorporate evolutionary improvements.

Figure 46. Metadata manager.

This plugin allows also including metadata under this Dublin Core (DC) standard as well as under the Open Graph Metadata (OG) standard in each published post.

Figure 47. Metadata manager settings.

```
<meta name="DC.Publisher" content="CS Track" />
<meta name="DC.Language" scheme="UTF-8" content="en-GB" />
<meta name="DC.Creator" content="CS Track" />
<meta name="DC.Description" content="&nbsp; [rt_reading_time label=Reading Time: postfix=minutes p
<meta name="DC.Type" scheme="DCMIType" content="Text" />
<meta name="DC.Format" scheme="IMT" content="text/html" />
<meta name="DC.Format.MIME" content="text/html" />
<meta name="DC.Format.SysReq" content="Internet browser" />
<meta name="DC.Source" content="https://cstrack.eu/">
<meta name="DC.Coverage" content="World">
<meta name="DC.Identifier" content="https://cstrack.eu/reports/evolution-academic-publications-cit.
<meta name="DC.Date" content="2020-12-31" />
<meta name="DC.Subject" content="Reports" />
<meta content="Ciberimaginario Divi Child Theme v.1.0" name="generator"/><style type="text/css">
img.wp-smilev.
```

Figure 48. Code with metadata in Dublin Core format.

With respect to each article, the title, meta description and target keywords are optimized to obtain the best snippets. In addition, a content analysis is carried out that includes social meta tags, keyword density, compliance with content accessibility requirements (alternative texts ...), headings, structured data, etc.

Figure 49. Article-level metadata editor.

5.1.5. REST API

The CS Track project, with the aim of promoting the reuse of its content on other platforms and external services, as well as web, mobile and desktop applications, makes it easy to query the WordPress REST API using URL syntax.

It is allowed to retrieve information from posts and pages, categories, tags and comments, among other resources.

The available Endpoints correspond to the documentation for developers of the WordPress REST API, available at <https://developer.wordpress.org/rest-api/reference/#rest-api-developer-endpoint-reference> with the mask <https://cstrack.eu/wp-json>

For example, to retrieve all categories you should use <https://cstrack.eu/wp-json/wp/v2/categories>

For each resource, the corresponding schema and the arguments to retrieve the contents in a specific way are indicated in the documentation.

Through API development platforms such as Postman, Endpoints can be tested and the arguments adjusted to retrieve the desired content.

```

117     }
118   },
119   {
120     "id": 22745,
121     "date": "2022-05-25T03:38:00",
122     "date_gmt": "2022-05-25T03:38:00",
123     "guid": {
124       "rendered": "https://cstrack.eu/?p=22745"
125     },
126     "modified": "2022-05-25T11:32:25",
127     "modified_gmt": "2022-05-25T09:32:25",
128     "slug": "expert-interviews-highlight-citizen-science-benefits-pitfalls-and-caveats-2",
129     "status": "publish",
130     "type": "post",
131     "link": "https://cstrack.eu/format/reports/
expert-interviews-highlight-citizen-science-benefits-pitfalls-and-caveats-2/",
132     "title": {
133       "rendered": "Expert interviews highlight citizen science benefits, pitfalls and caveats"
134     },
135     "content": {
136       "rendered": "\n<p>The CS Track research team, led by partners Christine Urban and Michael&
nbsp; Strähle from the Wissenschaftsladen Wien &#8211; Science Shop Vienna, has published
a report called <a href=\"https://zenodo.org/record/6045639#.Yg4zSu7MIId4\"
target=\"_blank\" rel=\"noreferrer noopener\"><strong>Conceptual Framework for Analytics
Tools</strong></a><strong>. </strong>This document builds on the preceding report <a
href=\"https://zenodo.org/record/5589618#.Yg4Pdu7MIId7\" target=\"_blank\"
rel=\"noreferrer noopener\">Framework Conceptual Model</a> and lays the conceptual
foundation for the project.&nbsp;This document maps citizen science landscapes in the
European Union and beyond, funding programmes, policies, advocacy and working groups, and
opportunities for participating in citizen science activities. Moreover, the report
presents an overview of educational citizen science activities in schools that
complements&nbsp;the previously published literature review on citizen science
activities in education. This document also includes interviews with African, Asian.

```

Figure 50. Example of content retrieved from an API development platform.

5.2. Annex 2. How to create a campaign on Mailchimp and integrate it into the website

Once replicated, click on it and edit whatever is necessary: name, subject, content... When it is finished and ready to be sent, click on the "Send" button at the top right, and it will be sent to all users subscribed to the newsletter.

Once submitted, we will get a link. This link is very important because with it, we will be able to share with anyone the content of the newsletter.

This is where the work in Mailchimp ends. However, the next step is to add the newsletter content to our website. The content of each newsletter is added to the WordPress page called "Newsletter". On this occasion, as it is a page, we work with

the Divi Builder. To do this, go to the "Newsletter" page. Here, click on the "Enable Visual Builder" tab to add the content of the last newsletter:

Figure 51. It is necessary to click on "Enable Visual Builder" to edit the page.

When we click here, we will be able to edit the content of the page with Divi Builder. The next step is to click on "Module settings" of the last module as shown in the following image.

Figure 52. Click on "Module settings".

When we click here, we will see the following table where we can edit the content of this module. Here, we must edit three sections: the text (title and content), the image, and the link.

Figure 53. Module settings.

- In the “Text” tab, add the title of the newsletter (e.g., 15 Newsletter | June 2022). The number indicates how many newsletters there are, then the corresponding month. In the content, add the titles of the articles published in the eMagazine.
- In the “Image & Icon” tab, a featured image of one of the articles published that month is chosen.
- In the “Link” tab, enter the link previously obtained in Mailchimp once the campaign has been sent.

Finally, when we have finished, click on the green tick, and save the changes. To attract new users to subscribe to the newsletter, a pop-up has been created.

Figure 54. Pop-up to subscribe to the newsletter.

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